

Winter Bird Feeding Project

AIMS:

- To increase our understanding of which birds will use raised feeders and what they prefer to eat.
- To assess whether this type of feeding overcomes problems with non-target species using the feeding stations.
- To inform Defra of the results to feed into future agri-environment option development for Supplementary feeding.

LOCATION OF FEEDERS:

- Locate feeders close to areas of wild bird seed mixes and/or next to other cover e.g. hedge.
- Fix to a post, high enough to be out of the reach of pheasants and, if possible, deer. Approx. 1m off the ground.
- Reduce risk of rats accessing feed through choice of location, design of feeding station and control.
- Suggestions include putting sheep hurdles around the feeder to keep deer off and tripod with feeder hanging down to prevent rats.

CAMERAS:

- Once set up and turned on the cameras will switch on and off themselves to record between 10am-11am and 3pm-4pm on the days they are running. They will take 5 sec video clips every 5 minutes during the hours they are running. These clips are sent via 4G signal to the Perdix server. You will be able to see your clips on the Perdix App. I will have access to them all and we will view them to compile species lists.
- Each Feeder will be monitored for 2 days per month (see project timeline). It is important that they run on the same days on each feeder to help standardise any results we get. If weather forecast very bad then we will move dates, co-ordinated through Whats-App group.
- Position camera on a post about 1.5m from feeders and pointing at the middle of 3 feeding holes, this should ensure all three are captured.
- Ideally point middle feeding hole towards hedge and put camera in front of hedge.
- Perdix suggest fixing camera on with strap for ease of taking on and off.
- Switch on: After 4pm the day before use or before 10am of the first day.
- Please take cameras in when not in use to reduce risk of theft and damage.
- Batteries will need to be supplied by yourselves and replaced/recharged before each monitoring period. Batteries may need to be replaced/recharged within a monitoring period.
- Ensure they are away from gates and footpaths to reduce risk of theft. I will also provide laminated signs to explain why they are there to use if you wish.

SEED MIXES:

- It is important that the right mix goes in each feeder to help with the monitoring. You will see on the Perdix Pro app which I have labelled Feeder 1 and which I have labelled Feeder 2. If you wish to switch, let me know and I will re-label.
- Feeder 1: Premium Finch Mix - small seeds, with a low percentage of wheat in it
- Feeder 2: Standard CS AB12 mix that includes 70% wheat.

PROJECT TIMELINE AND TASKS:

I will send reminders and amendments due to weather via What's-App

- 13th & 14th December: Trail camera record Feeder 1 with no feed
- 15th & 16th December. Trail camera record Feeder 2 with no feed
- **Monday 19th December. Start feeding.**
- Feeders to be checked regularly to ensure constant supply of seed. Record the amount of seed added and any that is disposed of so we can measure how much is required during the winter for a feeder.
- Clean regularly to minimise the risk of transmitting disease within wild bird populations.
- 23rd & 24th January. Trail camera record Feeder 1
- 25th & 26th January. Trail Camera record feeder 2
- 3rd-19th Feb. Targeted farmland bird surveys
- 20th & 21st February. Trail camera record Feeder 1
- 22nd & 23rd February. Trail camera record Feeder 2
- 27th & 28th March. Trail camera record Feeder 1
- 29th & 30th March. Trail camera record Feeder 2
- 24th & 25th April. Trail camera record Feeder 1
- 26th & 27th April. Trail camera record Feeder 2
- 30th April. Feeding to finish
- Keep a diary to record how much is being fed and thrown away each week. Also note signs of 'pests' – deer, rats, pigeons

In-kind time per farmer is estimated at 4 days based on 0.5 days installing feeding stations and cameras, 1.5 hours per week maintaining feeders, and updating records and 3 hours undertaking targeted farmland bird count surveys.

MONITORING:

- **Baseline:** The camera footage taken before feeders are installed. The targeted Big Farmland Bird count will include an area of bird mix with no feeding station to provide a control.
- **Cameras.** Linked to the PerdixPro monitoring platform. To provide a list of species (and a measure of numbers) that have benefitted from the feeders and also monitor 'pests'.

